

Identification of critical
forested areas
PERIOPSIS LTD

A.1. GENERAL PROJECT INFORMATION	
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Introduction

Climate change is a major challenge for European forests, particularly in the South Mediterranean region, where frequent heat waves, prolonged droughts have been observed, followed by large wildfires in Cyprus, Greece, and Turkey. IPCC projections indicate a high risk of desertification in the region. Climate change is likely to lead to disturbances to Mediterranean forests, thus the urgency of adopting adaptation measures.

Climate-Smart Forestry (CSF) offers a comprehensive approach to address these challenges by integrating sustainable forest-management practices that simultaneously enhance resilience, store carbon and sustain rural livelihoods. The EduCyprus-CSF project aims to build awareness and share knowledge of CSF in Cyprus through a range of activities for local stakeholders.

Within this project, PERIOPSIS employed multispectral satellite imagery and GAEA, a highly novel geospatial tool that offers - among other services - forestry analytics via geoinformatics and remote sensing, to detect, assess and prioritise ten forested areas with disturbance challenges due to soil erosion, previous wildfires, water stress and more.

Direct communication with relevant stakeholders, including community mayors, local NGOs and forestry experts took place to validate the results and explore the causes of detected disturbances. The results of this study will be shared with the Cyprus Department of Forests and other national and local stakeholders.

Additionally, the findings of this study will drive a series of engagement and outreach activities designed to raise awareness of CSF-based restoration strategies and the wider importance of Mediterranean forests. These initiatives will empower communities and decision-makers alike to actively shape CSF-oriented policies and on-the-ground interventions.

Study Area

The study focused on the forested areas controlled by the Republic of Cyprus, particularly those of the Troodos mountain. The Troodos Mountain is characterised by its rich biodiversity and flora, hosting “a variety of tree species each with distinct ecological characteristics and significance” [1]. The forests of Troodos provide vital ecosystem services and biodiversity. These forests, primarily dominated by pine (*Pinus brutia*) and cedar (*Cedrus brevifolia*) trees, face increasing threats from wildfires, prolonged droughts, pest outbreaks (notably the processionary caterpillar - *Thaumetopoea wilkinsoni*), and other disturbances, exacerbated by climate change.

Methodology

This study builds upon and complements our [recent work](#) which involved country-wide mapping and classification of tree species, applied across Cyprus (areas under the control of the Republic of Cyprus), using satellite imagery and deep learning techniques. This work provided an essential baseline for future forests monitoring, and enabled future work towards tracking forest health and detecting forest disturbances while linking detected anomalies to specific species' vulnerability. This study produced maps of forest and tree cover, covering the classification of 13 dominant tree species, including 6 forestry classes.

Top: Cyprus 9 Class Tree Mapping
Bottom: Pine Nigra and Pine Brutia distribution in Cyprus

For the purpose of this study, we collected and analysed satellite multispectral imagery (Sentinel-2) from October 2016 to October 2024, aiming for a minimum cloud coverage of 10%. For months where imagery with 10% cloud coverage was unavailable, data with the lowest possible cloud coverage was used to ensure that at least one record is available for each month.

We conducted spatiotemporal analysis focusing on the following indices:

- **NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index for greenness)**
- **NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index for vegetation water content), and**
- **NDWI (Normalized Difference Water Index for surface/canopy wetness).**

These indices were used to detect anomalies and changes indicative of forest disturbances. Large drops in NDVI or NDMI signalled vegetation loss or stress, while low NDWI highlighted areas of possible water stress or drying streams. The Land Use Change services of the GAEA portal was utilized to cross validate the results. Additionally, direct communication and meeting with community mayors, local NGOs and forestry experts took place to validate the results and elaborate on the causes of detected disturbances.

The results presented below summarise the prioritized areas, their locations, disturbances, and the indices/tools used in detection. Subsequent sections describe each area's situation and recommended CSF practices.

Results – Critical Forested Areas

After detecting and assessing and filtering out of a list of 23 remote-sensing detections, our study refined the priority list to the 15 most critical forested areas. These locations include disturbances such as recent wildfires, drought stress anomalies, and pest outbreaks identified in the NDVI/NDMI/NDWI time series. The updated list is available below:

1. West of Monastery of Archangel Michael, Kataliontas and towards Kapedes

Coordinates: 37.05260, 41.61062

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Severe water stress; processionary caterpillar (*Thaumetopoea wilkinsoni*, Tams) outbreak. It appears usually around February - March it comes down and starts to eat the tree.

2. Between the villages of Agios Epifanios & Mitsero

Coordinates: 36.86834, 41.66602

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: There have been wildfires before (around 2012-2013). The area is forest. It is a young pine forest. There is a processionary caterpillar (*Thaumetopoea wilkinsoni*, Tams), it has always been there, it is not a phenomenon of the last few years. Previously spraying was conducted, then replaced with biological drugs. Nowadays, spraying is only done on some farms. Drought attracts caterpillar (eats the leaf, restricts transpiration which is kind of a defense). Community council

actions: we act in case of fire, have our own first aid team to fight fire.

3. Between Kalavassos Mine II and Chirokitia

Coordinates: 37.06664, 41.37625

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: The incident is from wildfires of the past 2 years. Potential post-fire erosion.

4. Area around Dipotamos Dam stretching towards Klavdia (West of the village)

Coordinates: 37.13829, 41.41837

Indexes used: NDVI

Main Disturbance: The incident is from past wildfires. Water stress and potential

post-fire erosion gullies

5. Area around Kykkos Monastery

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Draught

6. North East of Pano Panagia

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Recurrent low NDVI patches (2018, 2019, 2024); drought/water stress.

7. All Western Side of Akamas

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Prolonged water stress/drought signature (NDVI drop since 2021). Potentially purposeful fires.

8. Curve starting from Frodisia to Cedar Calley and ending towards Milikouri, and then between Chionistra and Amiantos Asbestos mine area.

Coordinates: 36.37384, 41.67658

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Drought stressed canopy.

9. Small area East of Cedar Hiking Path Point

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Draught/Water stress

10. West of Palaichori dam - Southwest of Lazanias & Northwest /west of Palechori Dam, East of Apliki

Coordinates: 36.90732, 41.55227

Indexes used: NDVI

Main Disturbance: Processionary moth (*Thaumetopoea wilkinsoni*) infestation; NDMI/NWI anomalies; steep terrain.

11. South of Amiantos Geopark

Coordinates: 36.69501, 41.50630

Indexes used: NDVI

Main Disturbance: Draught

12. East of Pano Panagia

Coordinates: 36.31075, 41.50625

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Wildfires

13. Slightly Northwest of Frodisia (Southwest of Alona (Αλώνια) and between Alona and Stavros tis Psokas Landing Pad)

Coordinates: 36.30381, 41.71987

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: Draught/Water stress

14. Kyparissia Forest - Southwest of Dierona (also detected in Difference/Comparison data)

Indexes used: NDVI (2024)

Main Disturbance: Wildfire of July 2023

15. Between the villages of Apesia, Apsou and Mathikoloni

Coordinates: 36.75600, 41.29553

Indexes used: NDMI & NDWI

Main Disturbance: August 2024 wildfire; low NDVI/NDWI; exposed south facing slopes

References

- [1] <https://superworld.cyens.org.cy/papers/remotesensing-16-04611-v2.pdf>